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Research Article

English Language Apprehension and Relationship Building Bonding among International Students in the College of Arts and Sciences at University Utara Malaysia

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the English language apprehension and interpersonal communication for 170 international postgraduate students, who study in the College of Art and Science, University of Utara Malaysia. The research objectives are: firstly, to determine to what extent international postgraduate students' attitudes influence English language pronunciation for interpersonal communication. Secondly, to examine the relationship between attitudes and English language apprehension towards the effectiveness of interpersonal communication, and thirdly, to examine the adoption levels of English language among the students. Based on the previous factors, a questionnaire survey was developed to investigate the relationship between Attitude-self disclosure and English language apprehension, and the building of bonding sense in interpersonal communication. The results provided in this study are reporting the information collected from the survey and the statistical analysis of the data collected. The data was analyzed using SPSS. The research also suggests a significant and negative impact of English language apprehension on building a bonding relationship ($r = -0.254$, $p < 0.01$). Since the majority of international postgraduate students agreed that the English language is an important and useful language in interpersonal communication, hence, for future studies, we should look at the importance of English language in the bonding relationship, besides, how the international postgraduate students in UUM improve their proficiency in English towards mastering the use of English language in interpersonal communication.

Keywords: Attitudes, English language apprehension, interpersonal communication, pronunciation.

1. Introduction

Without a good communication, trusting, open relationship, motivation drops, performance suffers, and neither the individuals, nor the organization, will be as successful as they could

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be. Communication takes place between individuals in an organization on many different levels. The awareness of communication in the organization is to improve its communication processes, environment, and productivity. Therefore, the value of an accurate communication assessment and degree of communication satisfaction, lies in the need to create an understanding of the current interpersonal communication effectiveness, determine organizational communication strengths and weaknesses, and develop communication strategies that enhance working relationships and sense of satisfaction. Generally speaking, non-speakers of English language need additional learning and training efforts to be able to communicate well using the language. Students' apprehension towards using English language for communication purposes constitute reticence, unwillingness to communicate, shyness, and predisposition to communicate have received extensive research and theoretical attention by scholars in communication and psychology. This has caused various concerns that apprehension towards the English language can disrupt interpersonal communication, and most especially between people of different communication ability in that language. Apprehension has been clearly established as a primary reason for communication avoidance and communication disruption in the first language Learner. It may be even so in preventing people from communicating in a second language and disrupting their communication. This, to a very great extent, can affect interpersonal communication among international students from diverse cultural settings.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Speaking, listening, reading and writing are essential elements in the process of education, and most important of all, these skills are vital for communication and interpersonal communication. It is common to find second language learners who are deficient in the use of the target language for communication purposes. Some are better than others. The proficiency and competency gaps in the target language in most cases are attributed by various factors like educational background, culture, geographical location, political, religious, and ethnic divisions, and stereotypes commonly held by the learners towards English (Power and Smith, 1980; Cammish, 1997). Even among different non-native users of English language, there are still some variations, some are better English users as a result of their exposure to the language, while others still have some difficulties in using it in communication.

Most of the time, many non-English speaking students choose to study outside of their countries for a number of reasons, that language exposure is part of it. Thus, the ability to use the global language (English) for interpersonal communication is very essential. Therefore, identifying the barriers will assist in the long way. They may travel for obtaining international degree. Similarly, Barker (1997) observed that for multiple specialist knowledge and the prestige of a "foreign" degree that qualifies them for better jobs with higher incomes. These factors are a combination of "push" and "pull" factors. Push factors mean the features of the home environment that are viewed by prospective students as unsatisfactory, which

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include restricted economic resources, fewer world-class institutions, degree of involvement in the world community, fewer doctoral and postdoctoral programs, lack of availability of specializations, limited access to funding (especially for junior investigators), poor career prospects, and adverse social or political conditions (Myles and Cheng, 2003; Cammish, 1997). On the other hand, pull factors are defined as features of a destination country, such as: better academic and technological facilities, better financial support, prestige of a foreign degree, social and personal links as well. But, this does not guarantee that the students' English language proficiency and competency are improving. The most important thing is how often they engage in interpersonal communication using English language. For international students in the University of Utara Malaysia, it is evident that students from the same country only use their national language for communicating with each other, rather than using English language. In addition, there are other issues to be highlighted that may pose barriers to interpersonal communication. All these could also attribute to the apprehension experienced by these set of students in communicating with English Language for interpersonal interaction. Wahba (1990) revealed from a study among Arab students, that the most prominent problem faced by Arab students in using English language for communication, is pronunciation. Pronunciation has been identified as a primary cause of apprehension towards the target language, which has affected a number of non-native speakers of English. Most of Arab learners with Arabic mother tongue are facing difficulty in English pronunciation. The majority of them are with strong native Arabic abilities, and when they have to communicate in English, their English pronunciation tends to sound like Arabic mother tongue (Jayaraman, 2010). English learner with positive attitudes are more likely confident and independence in their English learning (Gan, 2004). Students who enjoyed their English classes and prefer social interaction with peers and teachers were showed positive attitudes towards English language as communication interaction. They were motivated and eager to learn without feeling stressful and constraints (Ghaith and Diab, 2008). Communication using English becomes challenging especially to non-English speakers. English language apprehension is due to negative attitudes such as lack of effort, lack of contact, unwillingness, anxiety and demotivating towards the use of English as communication language (Csizier et al, 2010). According to Michieka, (2005) in Kenya, Kenyan people are hesitant and hostile to the English language. Although negative attitudes towards English language are seen among rural and the not educated in Kenyan. Therefore, this study will explain the relationship between attitudes, English language apprehension and its effect on interpersonal communication among UUM international students. According to Edmondson et al, (2009) the commonest problem involved with communication deals with the difference in race, ethnicity and diversity of language to create a conclusive culture. Since the largest proportion of International postgraduates' students in UUM are of Middle East and South East Asian origin; the language problem is causing issues in interpersonal communication. Language learning in UUM deserves special attention, as a large percentage of these students will probably prefer to communicate using their native language instead of

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English (principal language using in UUM). The answer to the key question_ ‘whether international postgraduate students receive an effective, affordable and comprehensive English language teaching for interpersonal communication’ is still unknown. Perceptions and attitudes of students, especially international postgraduate students who are less commonly examined, how those attitudes are formed and how profoundly they impact interpersonal communication and use, are yet to be determined. Therefore, this study also suggests attaining international postgraduate students’ attitudes through surveys and questionnaires to provide an indication of whether course material is of satisfactory quality and appropriate to help meet their needs. Such qualitative information and analysis can be of great value to interpersonal communication strategy in UUM environment, and will be used as the basis to increase and improve the quality of communication system in UUM environment. Our particular interest is in the attitude, practice and implications of English language for interpersonal communication in the learning environment. By investigating the international postgraduate experiences of those using English language, our aim is to inform on interpersonal communication and to pick some of the reality of English language for interpersonal communication in university. We intend to highlight emergent issues of interpersonal communication and to raise questions that need further research, the importance of which cannot be underestimated; if interpersonal communication does continue to grow and become a predominant communication method of choice, its effective use will have a major impact on learning institutions and students.

1.2 Research Questions

To achieve the above objectives, this study intends to answer the following research questions:

1. What extent international postgraduate students’ attitudes influence English language for interpersonal communication?
2. What is the relationship between English language apprehension and_the effectiveness of interpersonal communication?
3. What are the adoption levels of English language among the students?

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study has a number of potential benefits that -are described below:

The identification of any obstacle will drive positive attitudes towards English language for interpersonal communication skills for international postgraduate._By identifying and knowing exactly the experience of international postgraduate students in the use of English language for interpersonal communication, it will permit to establish support structures and develop training programs tailored to the specific needs of the participants, in order to alleviate their difficulties and support the use of educational communication. Knowing exactly how international postgraduate students feel about English language for interpersonal

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communication will permit to manage the psychological aspects of the process and offer motives for the adoption and use of English language for interpersonal communication skills among them.

The primary contribution of this study is that it will assist the university management to understand the problems faced by their international students and to devise strategies as recommended to solve this problem. Such effort will allow the students to achieve their aims of studying outside their country. As such, this study would be able to suggest and recommend changes and practices that could improve interpersonal communication using English language. This will help the students to know what can motivate them in using English language for the purpose of interpersonal communication purposes.

Moreover, to prevent English language for interpersonal communications in UUM from losing out, this study is significant in providing an exploratory knowledge of English language for interpersonal communication in UUM. Searching literatures and conducting surveys will produce an overview of English language for interpersonal communication in UUM. Furthermore, this study aims to examine whether English language for interpersonal communication is able to generate positive attitudes among international postgraduate learners or vice versa. By doing this, UUM should be able to effectively plan and implement better quality English language for interpersonal communication for international postgraduate students, with good recognition and better acceptance by international postgraduate students, English language for interpersonal communication can fully realize its full potential in helping students to learn. In the long run, English language for interpersonal communication methods may play a significant role in the UUM institution and improve quality of education. By conducting a survey on learners, i.e. international postgraduate students, the study aims to gain a better understanding of their perspective towards the English language for interpersonal communication as an effective communication method. For international postgraduate students who are not aware of these interpersonal communication skills, this study can instill the awareness of interpersonal communication and create a learning possibility for them. Their exposure to this study can trigger their thoughts and mind to further improve themselves. By becoming more aware of interpersonal communication skills, international postgraduate students can add values to their qualifications and skills.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The scope and power of interpersonal communication are vast. This will be restricted to international students of University Utara Malaysia who are non-speakers of English language on their apprehension towards the use of English Language for interpersonal communication. These students are motivated to undertake their education in a new community for this singular reason. The researcher is interested in conducting a quantitative study to determine the problems encountered by these set of students while communicating using English language and how such identified problems can be tackled. In addition, this

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study also focuses on international postgraduate students' perceptions towards English language for interpersonal communication in UUM. This study was conducted by taking a small sample of international postgraduate students in UUM and distributing the survey questionnaires that related to this topic. Hence, the findings can be true to the context within this study.

2. Interpersonal communication

The Ministry of Education in Malaysia has seen the interpersonal communication as meaningful strategy to increase the level of networking and interpersonal skills with creativity and inventiveness for students (Sharif and Son, 2001). Ali and Ismail, (2006), stated that language is obtained most successfully when it is learned for communication in meaningful and significant social situations in Malaysia. Basic interpersonal communication skills; *"represents the language used by students when talking about everyday things in concrete situations, that is, situations in which the context provides cues that make understanding not totally dependent on verbal interaction alone"* (Ali and Ismail, 2006; p. 74). In the Malaysian context, in order to polish interpersonal communication skills in higher education institutions, the implementation of technology in teaching and learning activity such as e-learning which has been adopted to facilitate the changing way in communication (Azizan, 2010). Collaborative approach, for example, has been applied for Malaysian undergraduates' students during English lesson. The approach is simple; the teachers need to ensure the students ability to use English in discussing and communicating with one another, in order to reduce the number of poor English students in universities (Maesin et al, 2009).

2.1 Definition of interpersonal communication

Intercultural communication form the way people assert with change, deliver messages across borders and cultures, and revert to the basic properties of time and space (Monge, 1998). Peltokorpi, (2010) defined intercultural communication as communication occur between people with different cultural backgrounds. Interpersonal communication is also known as a *"being, relating to, or involving relations between persons"* (Smith, 2005; p.518). Interpersonal communication also means *"the means by which organisational activities, such as managing, controlling, planning, and leading are delivered"* (Bambacas and Patrickson, 2008; p.52). Interpersonal communication may affect the body of the message, the interaction between communicators and their credibility and lead to interpretation (decoding) of the message received by the individual (receiver) (Bambacas and Patrickson, 2008).

2.2 Communication apprehension

Literally, communication apprehension is synonymous to communication anxiety which can be defined as an individual's level of exercised fear or anxiety resulting from either real or anticipated communication with another person or persons (McCroskey, 1997). For instance, this anxiety is significant, because it adds to people understanding of the cognitive processes behind communication, assumed not to be a mindless behavior. In other words, people have

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the power to choose to communicate whether to communicate or not to as the case may be. In any of the cases i.e whether a person is willing or not to communicate, either in a given instance or more generally, is a volitional choice which is cognitively processed. Therefore, it can be added that the personality of the individual may be a determining factor in the manner in which that choice is made and what that choice will be (McCroskey and Richmond, 1990). On the other hand, Scott and Timmerman (2005) claimed that communication apprehension is not the only factor that affects an individual's decision whether or not to communicate. It rather plays a significant role. They added that communication apprehension theory posits that high-apprehension individuals are less likely to engage in communication than low-apprehension individuals. This is due to the fact that communication apprehension is believed to be a personality trait; it remains relatively consistent across different communication scenarios. Situational characteristics play a role in determining how much a person might communicate. The Personal Report of Communication Apprehension (PRCA) was administered to students from colleges in Australia, Korea, Japan, and University of Hawaii. Their results indicated that Americans were significantly more apprehensive than Australians and Koreans. The Japanese sample had the largest percentage of high apprehensive (Klopf and Cambra , 1979). Although some definitions may vary, all seem to include ideas of distress, fear and anxiety, or negative reactions toward interacting with others (Smith et al, 1994; McGuire et al, 1995). This serves as a good source of the independent variables for this study. Aside from having many different definitions of communication apprehension, there are also many different levels of communication apprehension to explore. In recent literature, communication apprehension has been discussed as having the distinction of both trait and state anxiety. McCroskey et al, (1986) revealed that there are actually four types of communication apprehension, Trait-like communication apprehension; Context-Based communication apprehension; Audience-Based communication apprehension; and Situational communication apprehension. With these four distinctions, there is no longer the dichotomy of an individual only having trait communication apprehension, or only having state communication apprehension, but now there is a continuum on which those characteristics can fall. The authors are of the belief that all human behavior as being solely trait-like or state-like disregards that connection that the two sources share.

2.2.1: Native language problem in English language pronunciation

The concept of pronunciation refers as “the sound system of the phonological features of a language, including individual vowels and consonant sounds and their combinations, as well as suprasegmental aspects such as rhythm and intonation” (Thielle, 2009; p.28). According to Thiele, (2009) the native language that match or related to English language may interfere the pronunciation. The issue of pronunciation error can be defined as “some deviation from a target or model pronunciation.” According to Menzel et al, (2000) non native English speakers are mainly produce many pronunciation errors which results negative feedback and

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cause obstacle during communication. Menzel et al, (2000) noted out the types of pronunciation errors that mainly occur among non-native English learners;

- Articulatory difficulties producing particular sounds or clusters of sounds (e.g., the notoriously difficult /th/ sound in English)
- Receptive difficulties, because of which the student is unable to perceive and therefore to reliably produce the distinction between two sounds (e.g., /ih/ and /iy/ for Italian speakers)
- Orthographic carry-over from the mother tongue; because so much of language use and learning is written, peculiarities of the student's native orthographic system may interfere with pronunciation of English (e.g., the sequence "IE" is pronounced as /iy/ in German, but can be pronounced in many ways in English.)
- Orthographic difficulties of English; because of the high degree of ambiguity mapping written to spoken English, the student may be expected to mis-apply or mis-generalize 'rules' of English pronunciation.

In Thailand, the problems occur among Thai students in English communication are they are too engaged with native language communication and Thai language has influenced when pronouncing English. Majority of Thai learners think English is very difficult to learn due to (Arunee, 2007);

- Interference from the mother tongue (Thai) particularly in pronunciation, syntax, and idiomatic usage.
- Lack of opportunity to use English in their daily lives.
- Unchallenging English lessons.
- Being passive learners.
- Being too shy to speak English with classmates.
- Lack of responsibility for their own learning.

In China, Ho, (1990) pointed out that majority students from Hubei, Henan and Shandong have the worst pronunciation English language problems. The strong mother tongue or native language Chinese dialects tend to produce some Chinese sound in English pronunciation. The common mistakes among Chinese students in English pronunciation are vowels, consonants intonation and diction. Giving an example mispronounced especially the words with 'r' and 'l'; a word such as "generally" is reduced into "gerali" , "world" becomes "word" , "curl" becomes "cur," "He doesn't want to sing" becomes "he doesn't want to sin" (Ho, 1990). In Arab countries, high educational institutions such as in Jordan, Oman, United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia, most of the students face difficulties in using English due to mistakes in pronunciation, spelling, morphology and as well as syntax (Rabab'ah 1997). The author had

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provided an example of Egyptian students are mainly facing problems in English language especially pronunciation;

“Egyptian students face certain problems related to pronunciation; intonation and most of these problems can be recognized to the differences between English and Arabic” (Rabab’ah 1997; p. 182)

In Turkey, the individual communicate English with native-like accent tend to be more likely encounter pronunciation difficulties. They are strong native language speakers since childhood and they are facing difficulty to pronounce English language properly with the words that consists of sound that never obtain a native like ascent, therefore, they are more like to communicate under the influence of mother tongue (Şenel, 2006).

2.2.2: English language apprehension

“Genuine community is a condition of togetherness in which people have lower their defenses and have learned to accept and celebrate their difference...”

(Monthienvichienchai et al, 2002; p.289).

Worldwide, English has considered become the first important lingua franca in communication. English is “routinely in evidence, publicly accessible in varying degrees, and part of the nation's recent or present identity” (Kameda, 2001; p.144). It has been estimated that two-third of world population do not practice English as a global lingua franca. In certain countries such as USA, Canada, Britain, South Africa, Australia, Ireland, New Zealand, and several Caribbean countries, English language has been spoken as a mother tongue in communication. Other countries such as Ghana, Nigeria, Singapore and India, English becomes officially first language in their countries. English is described as second language because the native language has considered mother tongue within their communities in their early life. Giving an example: Middle East, German, French and several countries in worldwide. (Crystal, 2003). Intercultural communication barriers arise from group differences in cognition and patterns of behavior (e.g. language, customs, communication styles, etc). Effective intercultural communication requires cognitive, affective, and behavioral (including linguistic) adaptations that can be arduous and troublesome to participants in an intergroup encounter (Dodd., 1995; Gudykunst, 1986, Lustig & Koester, 1996). Communication with the culturally different is frequently associated with adverse emotional responses (Gudykunst & Hammer, 1988; Neuliep & McCroskey, 1997; Stephan & Stephan, 1985; Yook & Albert, 1999). To illustrate, individuals may feel awkward and anxious when interacting with culturally different others (Stephan & Stephan, 1985), in part, because of communication obstacles. Members of a dominant ethno linguistic group may experience feelings of impatience and frustration when communicating with non-native speakers of a language (Dodd, 1995; Giles & Robinson, 1990; Wiseman & Koester, 1993). Although accented speech is sometimes viewed as socially attractive, processing accented

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speech is cognitively and emotionally taxing (Yook & Albert, 1999), and non-native speakers of language are rated less favorable than native speakers on a wide range of attributes, including competence and trustworthiness (Edwards, 1982). According to Fletcher, (2006) English is not spoken language among international students widely. Majority of them have greater attached with their mother tongue, they were born in non-English speaking countries and they often do not speak English at home. The students also more likely are more receptive to sites in their native language although the fact that the vital course of study will be in English. In Saudi Arabia, the early history of Saudi Arabia, there was a general unwillingness to teach English and other foreign languages as well. The role of English implemented in Saudi has significantly influenced cultural and religious role. It has been noted that if more English is being teach, it means “less Islam”. These factors affected the continued of English status in Saudi Arabia as a poor second language (Elyas and Picard, 2010). The author also stated that even university graduates also have poor command in English communication.

“[. . .] very weak in communication skills; they cannot write not only in English but also in Arabic too. They cannot communicate verbally as well as they should. They cannot make a presentation. [. . .] and there is [sic] a major issue, which are weak analytical skills”

(Elyas and Picard, 2010; p.143).

In Saudi Arabia, certain sector aggressively anti-English to be learns and to be teaches. In order to support the education of foreign languages, they used Hadith as slogan (especially English language centers) to attract Saudi Arabian to learn English and other languages as well (Elyas and Picard, 2010). The famous Hadith as follows; *“من تعلم لغة قوم امن مكرهم”*

“He whoever learns other people’s language will be secured from their cunning” (Elyas and Picard, 2010; p.141). In Japan for example, refer to Kamada, (2001) Japanese are poor command of English which lower than North Korea and Taiwan. Japanese are not good user of English due to their communication styles are indirect expression or not straight to the point (roundabout manner). Most Japanese prefer to speak with their close friend and the language habits are low status verbal communication and focus more on humility than the point itself. “ “Yes” does not always mean yes in Japan, but there are some 16 ways to avoid saying no, and it is not in the Japanese tradition to call a spade a spade” (Imai, 1975 In: Kamada, 2001:p. 145).In New Zealand education system, majority international students whose first language is not English communicate very poor English. Most of International students’ perceptions toward English language are; English is not easy to be learned without experience of living and communicating in an English speaking community. Due to poor conversation in English, most of International students are lack participation in class discussion, group work and the students typically silence to avoid making mistakes in communication (Selvarajah, 2006). According to Selvarajah (2006), Many Asian students who come from non-English speaking families with different cultural background results lack of ability in the English language. They also facing difficulties to understand the course

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especially in business and social science where English language is must. Therefore, many Asian students prefer a method of examination than a group of assessment or individual assessment. The challenges of international students are language, communication and learning styles. The native language as a method of communication makes English less use for communication. In addition communication differences also affect communication in terms of native idioms and slang may lead cultural misunderstandings (Varga-Atkins and Ashcroft, 2004). In addition, culture behavioral styles have been postulated to be reflected with understandable English language. Asian languages use hints and indirect English language to address their idea directly (Song, 2008).

2.2.3: Attitude-self disclosure

According to Michieka, (2005) attitudes refer as people mind's towards something and should be marked in their actions. Attitudes can be changed and depends on time and caused factors. Refer to Gan, (2004) attitudes towards self-directed learning depends on psychological of the individuals, their perceptions towards the objects and their leaning behaviors. The author also noted that attitudes can be either positive or negatives depend on the learner's behavior. Within psychology, research on intercultural communication has contributed greatly to our understanding of ethnolinguistic identify, language attitudes, speech accommodation, and the significance of language in stereotyping (Giles & Johnson, 1981; Giles & Robinson, 1990). Intercultural communication scholars and educators have called for more research on intercultural communication within social psychology, for example, is the relationship between intercultural communication barriers and intergroup attitudes (Gudykunst & Hammer, 1988; Wiseman, Hammer, & Nishhida, 1989).

2.2.3.1: Positive attitudes

Native speaker attitudes towards varieties of "*English speech have demonstrated that standard varieties tend to be judged positively in terms of 'status', and hence are frequently rated highly on traits such as ambition and intelligence*" (McKinzie, 2008; p. 64). Refer to Charkova, (2007) there are two types of positive learners' i.e, integrativeness and attitudes toward learning.

- Integrativeness

Learner's motivation to recognize with a certain language community

- Attitudes

Learners' satisfaction with the teaching context

English learner with positive attitudes are more likely confident and independence in their English learning (Gan, 2004). Students who enjoyed their English classes and prefer social interaction with peers and teachers were showed positive attitudes towards English language

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as communication interaction. They were motivated and eager to learn without feeling stressful and constraints (Ghaith and Diab, 2008). According to Abedi and Gandara, (2007) students who are willing to take challenge learning English and other cultures as well lead to a good in English and cultural knowledge performance compared to those who are afraid to do so. According to Michieka, (2005) in Kenya, Kenyan people are hesitant and hostile to the English language. Although, negative attitudes towards English language can be seen among rural and lack of education Kenyan, however, Kenyan youngster especially students recognized English is useful language and need to be learnt. In addition, students with positive attitudes towards English language thought that English is a beautiful language and plays as an international language.

2.2.3.2: Negative attitudes

In Japan, according to Matsuda, (2003), Japanese students view English as non-international language and not belonged to international community. In addition, it has been noted that Japanese students were facing difficulty to communicate in English due to they often communicate with their native language. In Arab, majority Arabian students feel discomfort to communicate and interact with others using English language. They are usually preferred to less to speak up, unwillingness to interact with peers and teachers, not interested with class activities (Ghaith and Diab, 2008). Language conflicts, lack of English use and insufficient established English language are the reasons many Turkish have negative perceptions towards English. In Turkey, students with negative attitudes show anxiety and feel discouragement (Doganacay-Aktuna and Kiziltepe, 2005). To illustrate, a prevalent view exists of foreign students as outsiders who are culturally maladjusted, native, and confused. They are seen as psychologically unbalanced individuals who suffer from a “foreign student syndrome”, a controversial condition characterized by disheveled appearance, a passive and withdrawn interpersonal style, and a multitude of psychosomatic ailment (Paige, 1990; Pedersen, 1991). In China, students with negative attitudes towards English are mainly because they felt their English was not good, felt bored with the English and as well as lost confidence (Gan et al, 2004). In German, according to Hilgendorf, (2007), the spread of English linguistics is difficult and ambiguous. The author noted that Germany people are often strong behavior; view and majority of them have negative attitudes towards foreign languages.

2.4 Theoretical Perspective

This study is based on Language Expectancy Theory under interpersonal and communication relation. The language Expectancy Theory is concerned about message strategies based on the assumption that language is a rule-governed system and that people develop expectations about the language message strategies used by others in persuasive ways. The theory emphasized the power of language in communication. The theory explains the need for certain degree of competence in a language to be used for communication if at all such communication has to be effective. This theory is directly related to this study since the

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interest is to know the effect of language barriers on inter-personal communication among foreign students.

2.4.1: Theory of communication apprehension

According to McCroskey et al, (1985: p.186) stated that communication apprehension is an “individual's level of fear or anxiety associated with either real or anticipated communication with another person or persons.” The theory of communication apprehension explained the phenomenon of communication apprehension related to avoidance. The theory of communication apprehension is generally about avoiding communication in the language due to fear communication factor and lack confidence about the ability with the second language (McCroskey et al, 1985). McCroskey, 1982 In: Wrench et al, (2002; p. 405) pointed out that communication apprehension can present itself along a four-point range;

1. As a trait- “it is understood that for some people high levels of CA are a biological part of one’s temperament.”
2. In a generalized context-“This view of communication apprehension recognizes those individuals who experience high levels of anxiety about communicating in a particular context or situation but who have much less or even no anxiety about communicating in other contexts.”
3. With a given individual or group across contexts-“ Under this manifestation of communication apprehension, an individual experiences high levels of communication apprehension when interacting with a specific person (teacher, supervisor, parent, etc...) or within a specific group (team at work, therapy group, board of directors, etc...)”
4. With a given individual or group in a given situation, “people again experience communication apprehension when interacting with a specific person or group, but this is not recurring communication apprehension and is relegated to a specific situation.”

The author emphasize that not everyone in any one culture share and have the same perceptions. McCroskey et al, (1984) pointed out that irrational and anxiety is incorporated into communication apprehension.

2.4.2: Dynamic systems theory

Dynamic system theory is approach to second language acquisition (De Bot et al, 2007). The author explained that dynamic system theory actually originally from two coupled variables in double pendulum (in mathematically) and becomes the science complex system. Complex system can be learning person towards sets of interacting variables i.e., “when dynamic system theory is applied to first language (language 1) or (language 2) communication, the main feature of a dynamic system theory is its change over time” (De Bot et al, 2007; p.10). De Bot et al, (2007) noted that dynamic system theory consists of 4 components;

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1. The systems change over time in which each state is a transformation of a previous state.
2. The systems have a complete interconnectedness where the variables in the system are connected and affect each other.
3. The systems are self-organizing into preferred states or so-called ‘attractor states’ and states that will not be preferred called ‘repeller states’. When variables influence the system, change is to be predictable.
4. The systems possess nonlinearity or so-called ‘the butterfly effect’. Even small changes in one part of the system may have great influence in the whole system.

Therefore, dynamic system theory is characterized as “*complete interconnectedness*” and can be used as an “*umbrella theory in language development.*” Dynamic system theory explained the reason why individual eager and refuse to speak English as a second language. (De Bot et al, 2007).

2.5 Theoretical Frame Work

Figure1. The theoretical framework of analyzing international postgraduate students’ perceptions towards attitude-self disclosure and English language apprehension towards relationship building bonding (Interpersonal communication) among international postgraduate students’ in UUM. The model is divided into two important parts, i.e. independent variable (attitude self-disclosure and English language apprehension) and a dependent variable (relationship building bonding among students). The relationship attitude self-disclosure and English language apprehension are significant beliefs that may affect the building bonding among international postgraduate students and from these, it may improve and provide an effective plan and as well as better quality interpersonal communication system for international postgraduate students in UUM.

2.6 Definition of operation

English language apprehension: Conceptual definition and operational definition:

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Independent variables

- Adoption of attitude self-disclosure applied in University of Utara Malaysia
- Adoption of English language apprehension in University of Utara Malaysia

2.6.1: Attitude

Attitudes are generally positive or negative views of a person, place, thing, or event—this is often referred to as the attitude object. People can also be conflicted or ambivalent toward an object, meaning that they simultaneously possess both positive and negative attitudes toward the item in question.

2.6.2: English language apprehension

Apprehension is not easy to define in a sentence. It is associated with feelings of uneasiness, frustration, and self doubt. Language apprehension is the fear or nervousness that occurs when a learner is expected to perform in the second or foreign language. This apprehension is directly linked to performing in the English language; it is not just a general performance apprehension. A lot of students experience apprehension when they are first exposed to the English language.

2.7 Hypothesis

Three hypotheses were developed based on the model of the study:

- H1:** There is a positive relationship between attitudes-self disclosure and relationship building.
- H2:** There is a negative relationship between English language apprehension and relationship building bonding.
- H3:** There are adoption levels of English language among students.

3.0 Methodology

The survey adopts a total view on the issue of usage and attitudes towards interpersonal communication, in terms of native language abilities and English language apprehension, taking into consideration the international postgraduate master students in the College of Art and Science. A survey research method will be used in this study. The purpose of this study is to acquire perceptions from international postgraduate master students in the College of Art and Science, towards the interpersonal communication in University of Utara Malaysia. A questionnaire survey technique is considered as the most suitable and practical method, and as the rational choice behind the research design or methodology.

3.1 Research Design

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As the purpose of this study will be to acquire perceptions from international postgraduate students regarding English language for interpersonal communication in University of Utara Malaysia, a questionnaire survey technique will be considered as the most suitable and practical method. An investigation on the research literature had enhanced the usage of questionnaire in social science research.

3.2 Data Analysis

Data will be analyzed quantitatively using simple descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation. Analysis was carried out using a statistical software package, namely SPSS. One hundred and seventy questionnaires will be distributed to all the respondents' i.e. international postgraduate master in College of Art and Science students (non-native English speakers) from each branch or faculty. Due to good support by the international postgraduate students in this institution, all questionnaires will be collected in a timely manner.

3.3 Correlation Factor

Relationships among the factors, Attitude-self disclosure and English language apprehension will be investigated using Pearson's Correlations. Pearson's Correlations will be calculated between interpersonal communication and each of factors; Attitude-self disclosure and English language apprehension. Regression analysis will be performed to identify the relationships among all possible covariates and leisure time physical activity. All data analyses will be performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

4.0 Analysis of Demographic Factor

The demographic factors in this study are gender, age, race, courses that they are enrolled in, language preference when having conversation with their peers, the period of time they are reside in Malaysia and how they rank the use of English communication as language for communicating in UUM.

4.1 Ranking of the use of English as language for communicating

Table 4.1.1 shows that 23 of the respondents thought that the use of English as language for communicating was not important, 144 of the respondents thought that it is important while 3 of the respondents have no idea.

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Table 4.1. Ranking of the use of English as language for communicating

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Not Important	23	13.5
Important	144	84.7
Don't know	3	1.8
Total	170	100.0

4.1.1: Living experience in Malaysia

Table 4.1.1 shows that 53 respondents were staying less than 1 year in Malaysia, 74 respondents were staying in Malaysia for 1-2 years and 43 respondents were staying 3 years or more in Malaysia.

Table 4.1.1: Living experience in Malaysia

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Less than 1 year	53	31.2
1-2 years	74	43.5
3 years or more	43	25.3
Total	170	100.0

4.2 Pearson Correlation:

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between attitudes-self disclosure and relationship building.

4.2.1 The correlation relationship building bonding and Attitude-self disclosure

Table 4.2.1 indicated that there is a significant and positive relationship between relationship building bonding and Attitude-self disclosure, ($r=.488$, $p < 0.01$). This shows that the more Attitude-self disclosure they have, the more relationship building bonding interpersonal communication.

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Table 4.2.1: The correlation relationship building bonding and Attitude-self disclosure

Relationship building bonding	
Attitude-self disclosure	r .488**
	P .000
	n = 170

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Hypothesis 2: There is a negative relationship between English language apprehension and relationship building bonding

4.2.2 Table 4.2.2 indicate that there is a significant and negative relationship between relationship building bonding interpersonal communication and English language apprehension, ($r = -.254$, $p < 0.01$). This shows that the more English language apprehension they have, the less relationship building bonding interpersonal communication.

Table 4.2.2 The correlation relationship building bonding and English language apprehension

Relationship building bonding	
English language apprehension	r -.254**
	P .000
	n = 170

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The main objective of this study is the attitude, practice and implications of English language for interpersonal communication in the learning environment. By investigating the international postgraduate experiences of those using English language, our aim is to inform on interpersonal communication and to pick some of the reality of English language for interpersonal communication in university. In this study also, we are intended to highlight

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emergent issues of interpersonal communication and to raise questions that need further research, the importance of which cannot be underestimated; if interpersonal communication does continue to grow and become a predominant communication method of choice, its effective use will have a major impact on learning institutions and students. In this study we had 170 respondents of international postgraduate master in College of Art and Science students at UUM. The discussions on these demographic profiles are highlighted afterwards.

5.0 The relationship between attitudes and relationship building bonding

The results provided for the hypothesis 1 that there is a positive relationship between attitudes and relationship building. The findings of this study showed that there is a positive relationship between attitudes and relationship building. Some previous findings support the empirical data. As with the findings of students who enjoyed their English classes and prefer social interaction with peers and teachers were showed positive attitudes towards English language as communication interaction. They were motivated and eager to learn without feeling stressful and constraints (Ghaith & Diab, 2008). This finding also related with the language Expectancy Theory is concerned about message strategies based on the assumption that language is a rule-governed system and that people develop expectations about the language message strategies used by others in persuasive ways.

5.1 The relationship between English language apprehension and relationship building bonding

The results provided for the hypothesis 2 was that there is a negative relationship between English language apprehension and relationship building bonding. The findings of this study showed that there is a negative relationship between English language apprehension and relationship building bonding. This is consistent with Csizier et al, (2010) which indicated that English language apprehension is due to negative attitudes such as lack of effort, lack of contact, unwillingness, anxiety and demotivating towards the use of English as communication language. In addition, this finding is consistent with, Selvarajah, (2006) who claimed that most of International students' perceptions toward English language are; English is not easy to be learned without experience of living and communicating in an English speaking community. Due to poor conversation in English, most of International students are lack participation in class discussion, group work and the students typically silence to avoid making mistakes in communication. In addition, this finding is consistent with, Scott and Timmerman (2005) who claimed that communication apprehension is not the only factor that affects an individual's decision whether or not to communicate. It rather plays a significant role. They added that communication apprehension theory posits that high-apprehension individuals are less likely to engage in communication than low-apprehension individuals. Also, Abedi and Gandara, (2007) found that students who are willing to take challenge learning English and other cultures as well in English and cultural knowledge performance compared to those who are afraid to do so. This finding also related with the communication apprehension theory. This is due to the fact that communication apprehension is believed to

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be a personality trait; it remains relatively consistent across different communication scenarios.

5.1.1: The adoption levels of English language among students.

The results provided for the hypothesis 3 were that there are adoption levels of English language among students. The present of the study shows that most of the international postgraduate students felt nervous if they have to speak in English without doing preparation. Moreover, most of them felt like they are different person and not sure about themselves when they spoke in English. Furthermore, they embarrassed to volunteer answer in class as they afraid that other students will have a bad perceptions toward them when they poorly speak in English.

6. Conclusion

From the survey of student's apprehension towards the usage of English language in communication reviewed that most of the postgraduate students were feeling awkward, embarrassed, uncomfortable, not relaxed, anxiety as well as nervous in speaking English with the other students and supervisor. Furthermore, most of them were not enjoying speaking English with their peers, as well as with other students. Although most of them think that English language is useful and important language, however, the apprehension towards the English language have disrupts interpersonal communication, and most especially between people of different communication ability in that language. Apprehension has been clearly established as a primary reason for communication avoidance and communication disruption in the first language Learner. It may be even so in preventing people from communicating in a second language and disrupting their communication. This, to a very great extent, can affect interpersonal communication among international students from diverse cultural settings. Apprehension towards English language serves as in the process of interpersonal communication since individual may be unwilling to engage in the practice in the language which is against the principle of language acquisition. On the other hand, most of them want to learn to speak in English as well as using English in a wide variety of situation. Most of them think that English is very useful and important and hence we should learn and adopt it. They also thought that English is not fun to use in communication as majority of them agreed that English is not their priority. This is in accordance to the survey in Section B, most of them prefer to speak in their native language instead of English as they thought that English is not their priority and not fun of using it in communication. English language for interpersonal communication face challenges especially among non-English speakers around the world. A primary concept of English language for interpersonal communication acts as effective interaction and communication, thus creating an effective communication among one and another. Since communication is a vital process to receive and delivering ideas or thoughts in an organization as well as in a society, hence the ability to use the global language (English language) for interpersonal communication is very essential.

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6.1: Future Research Suggestions

Since majority of the international postgraduate students agreed that the English language is an important and useful language in the interpersonal communication, hence for the future studies, we should look at the important of English language in the relationship bonding as well as how the international postgraduate students in UUM improve their proficiency in English towards mastering the use of English language in interpersonal communication. Furthermore, based on the limitations highlighted and the recommendations presented above.

English language for interpersonal communication face challenges especially among non-English speakers around the world, thus creating an effective communication among one and another. Since communication is a vital process to receive and delivering ideas or thoughts in an organization as well as in a society, hence the ability to use the global language (English language) for interpersonal communication is very essential. Therefore identifying the barriers will assist in a long way.

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